

Supplementary Table S3. Bacteria strain list.

Strain	Description	Reference
<i>Vibrio cholerae</i>		
<i>V. cholerae</i> C6706 El Tor biotype (Wild type)	Wild type strain	Waters Lab Collection
<i>V. cholerae</i> $\Delta aceE$ (VC2414)	Isogenic deletion strain	This study
<i>V. cholerae</i> $\Delta aceF$ (VC2413)	Isogenic deletion strain	This study
<i>V. cholerae</i> $\Delta pfIA$ (VC1869)	Isogenic deletion strain	This study
<i>V. cholerae</i> $\Delta lacZ$ (VC2338)	Isogenic deletion strain	This study
<i>V. cholerae</i> $\Delta toxT$ (VC0838)	Isogenic deletion strain	Waters Lab Collection
<i>V. cholerae</i> pMMB66EH (empty vector)	Complementation verification strain	This study
<i>V. cholerae</i> $\Delta aceE$ pMMB66EH (empty vector)	Complementation verification strain	This study
<i>V. cholerae</i> $\Delta aceE$ pMMB66EH- <i>aceE</i>	Complementation verification strain	This study
<i>V. cholerae</i> $\Delta aceF$ pMMB66EH (empty vector)	Complementation verification strain	This study
<i>V. cholerae</i> $\Delta aceF$ pMMB66EH- <i>aceF</i>	Complementation verification strain	This study
<i>V. cholerae</i> $\Delta pfIA$ pMMB66EH (empty vector)	Complementation verification strain	This study
<i>V. cholerae</i> $\Delta pfIA$ pMMB66EH- <i>pfIA</i>	Complementation verification strain	This study
<i>Escherichia coli</i>		
<i>E. coli</i> MCH100 λ pir pKAS32 (empty vector)	Plasmid vector strain	Lab Collection
<i>E. coli</i> S17 pMMB66EH (empty vector)	Plasmid vector strain	Lab Collection
<i>E. coli</i> S17 λ pir 3-7	Cloning vector recipient	Lab Collection